

Teachers' willingness in implementing modular distance learning: The basis for PLEP innovation

Yacasel E. Alejo ■ Don Vicente C. Real

Abstract

The study examined the teachers' willingness in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL) toward transactional distance (TD) as the basis for present level of educational performance (PLEP) innovation in Tayasan District I, Division of Negros Oriental, the School Year 2020-2021. The study was a descriptive type. The survey questionnaire using Google Forms was utilized and sent to the teacher-respondents online. Data gathered were statistically treated using frequency distribution method and analyzed using percentage, weighted mean, and Chi-square Test at 0.05 level of significance using the software Interactive Chi-square Test of Kristopher J. Preacher. The findings revealed that 97 or 71.85% of the 135 teacher respondents are female within the age category of 31 and below; 74.81% of the respondents earned units in the master's degree; and 40 or 29.63% of them had attended in-service training at the regional level. Respondents have shown a very willing descriptive rating in the implementation of the MDL toward the transactional distance. Parents' low educational background resulting in less desire in coaching their children as the highest deterrent factor in the implementation of MDL. Hence, the PLEP is formulated to provide intervention activities on the prevalent deterrent factor in the implementation of MDL amid the -19 pandemic. Teachers were very willing and supportive in the implementation of MDL in Tayasan District 1 in School Year 2020-2021 through the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) of the Department of Education to ensure that learning opportunities were provided to the students through the different modalities among others. However, teachers' highest in-service training attended has a significant relationship with the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL. It is crystal clear that there was a wide disparity in transactional distance between teacher and learner's dialogue due to the use of modular distance learning, completely wanting of face-to-face instruction, hence; asynchronous. But on the other hand, the transactional distance was lessened due to the strong bilateral partnership between teachers and parents (who represented their children in receiving the learning materials in module forms), in mentoring their children (enrolled in the school year 2020-2021) in the teaching-learning process which took place at home.

Keywords: Transactional distance. Modular distance learning. Pandemic. Implementation. PLEP.

Yacasel E. Alejo

Bago Elementary School, Davao City, Davao del Sur, Philippines

Don Vicente C. Real*

*Villaflores College, Tanjay City, Negros Oriental, Philippines
donvicentereal@gmail.com*

***Corresponding author**

Introduction

Distance Learning (DL) is the adopted learning modality in the world's educational landscape at present due to the resurging presence of COVID-19 after it was contained for a year or more. In the first world countries, it has long been practiced, but not in the Philippines except for some schools which adopted blended learning at the inception of their schools' operation. As an educational strategy, distance education has eminent and essential features which can cater to the learning needs of the learners as they learn from the comfort of their own home, but with the guidance and direction provided by the teachers who prepared the instructional materials, the course syllabi, or modules and who facilitated the actual delivery of the lessons through virtual instruction (Alea et al., 2020; Bozkurt, 2019). In a similar direction, parents have significant roles in the process.

In response to the pandemic, the Department of Education issued Order No. 12, s. 2020, An Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) for the School Year 2020-2021 to ensure that learning opportunities are given to learners in a safe manner, through different learning delivery modalities. DepEd introduced various alternative learning delivery modalities depending on students' available resources. On the other hand, while home-schooling programs are already being offered by private schools and accredited home-school providers, the implementation of homeschooling in public schools is considered a new practice, and the policies for its implementation are still being developed. However, the learning continuity plan (LCP) emphasizes that DepEd must adopt alternative modes of delivery of learning where face-to-face learning is not possible. Moreover, the LCP identifies three learning delivery modalities (LDMs) that schools may implement: distance learning (DL), blended learning (BL), and home-schooling (HS). Thus, only the modular distance learning (MDL) option is adopted by the public schools using distance learning. The policies for its implementation are still being developed.

Methodology

The researchers adopted a quantitative research design. The survey questionnaire forms were utilized in data gathering relative to the teachers' willingness to implementation of MDL in pandemic time. It is a descriptive study because it has described the status of an independent variable which is the teachers' profile. Furthermore, it is a correlational study because it attempts to determine the extent of the relationship between two or more variables which establish a relationship between the teachers' profile and teachers' willingness in the implementation of the MDL, and the teachers' profile and the deterrent factors as a basis for present level of educational performance (PLEP) innovation.

The Municipality of Tayasan is the local of the study. It is one of the nineteen (19) municipalities and six (6) cities in the province of Negros Oriental. It is a third-class municipality with a population of approximately 40,000 people including children. It is composed of 28 barangays with an area of 154.20 km²/59.54 square miles which constitutes 2.86% of Negros Oriental's total area. The municipality is composed of thirty-one (34) public schools – five (5) secondary schools and twenty-six (26) elementary schools and three (3) private schools. It is divided into two (2) districts namely Tayasan District 1 and Tayasan District 2. Tayasan 1 has four (4) public secondary schools, eleven (11) public elementary schools, and one (1) private elementary school. Tayasan 2 has two (2) public secondary schools, fourteen (14), public elementary schools, and two (2) private secondary schools.

The respondents of this study are the elementary and secondary public-school teachers in Tayasan District 1. The target sample size is at least seventy-five (75%) of the total population of teachers from each school.

To determine relevant data for this study, the researcher developed a questionnaire in three (3) parts - these consist of the, (1) respondents' profile, (2) extent of teachers' willingness, and the (3) deterrent factors. It was statistically tested for its reliability and validity using the Cronbach's Alpha (α) with 0.80 reliability and validity through the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS Application). The pre-testing was done outside the local of the study.

The survey questionnaire was utilized to determine the teachers' willingness in the implementation of MDL. The data gathering procedure was done using the Google Forms, which were sent to the teacher-respondents online. Retrieval of the forms was done in the same procedure.

The random sampling technique was used to provide every respondent in a research universe to get the opportunity to be selected and participate in the study. Permission to administer the questionnaire forms to the respondents in the different schools in Tayasan District was secured first. The statistical tools used were the frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, Chi-square, Likert's 5- Point Scale. Furthermore, the test of the significant relationship between two variables was dealt with using the Interactive Chi-square Test by Kristopher J. Preacher (2001).

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Profile of the respondents in terms of gender (n=135)

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Male	38	28.15	2
Female	97	71.85	1
Total	135	100.00	

As indicated that out of 135 teachers, 38 are males and 97 are females. One may safely conclude that the overall results reveal that most of the teachers in Tayasan District I are females with a percentage of 71.85%.

According to the study by Bongco and Abenes (2019), the Filipino formal educational system is being patterned from the United States, that the female teachers' working circumstances were also passed down and perpetuated in the Philippine educational system. Further, she added that at present, even though the profession has advanced much over time, it is still largely regarded as "woman's work," which is often associated with lower prestige and remuneration. Moreover, it is therefore conceived that the above results imply that there are more women in the teaching profession nowadays.

Table 2. Profile of the respondents in terms of age (n=135)

Age	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
31 and below	50	37.04	1
31 to 37	31	22.96	2
38 to 44	30	22.22	3
45 to 51	12	8.89	4
52 to 58	8	5.93	5
59 to 65	4	2.96	6
Total	135	100.00	

The respondents' profile in terms of age is grouped into five (5) categories: 31 to 37 years old; 38 to 44 years old; 45 to 51 years old; 52 to 58 years old; and 59 to 65 years old. The table further presents its corresponding frequency, percentage, and rank. The first age group has 50 respondents with 37.04%, rank 1; the second age group has 31 respondents with 22.96%, rank 2; the third age group has 30 respondents with 22.22%, rank 3; the fourth age group has 12 respondents with 8.89%, rank 4; the fifth group age category with 8 respondents, 5.93%, rank 5; and the sixth age group, 4 or 2.96%, rank 6. This implies that an overwhelming majority of the teachers in Tayasan District 1 are in the age category of 31 and below.

Moreover, this table shows the age categories of the respondents who completed the questionnaires and the allocation of questionnaires to various age groups was in no way affected by bias. Hence, a true reflection of the researcher's impartiality in the distribution and answering of questionnaires was done.

Table 3. Profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment (n=135)

Educational attainment	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Bachelor's Degree (BEED/BSED)	48	35.56	2
With Master's Units	74	54.81	1
Master's Degree	11	8.15	3
With Doctoral Units	2	1.48	4
Total	135	100.00	

As illustrated, out of 135 respondents, 48 or 35.56% are holders of bachelor's degree, rank 1; 74 or 54.81% have master's units; 11 or 8.15% are master's degree holder, rank 3; and 2 or 1.48% of the respondents have doctoral units, rank 4.

The results further reveal that majority of the respondents are enrolled in the graduate programs to achieve mastery of a specialized field of study, the development of original and critical thinking, and the demonstration of problem-solving skills that prepare the degree holder for advanced instruction and leadership positions in the areas of research, creative work, and professional practice, as well as to achieve clear progression beyond basic education baccalaureate/undergraduate education (CHED M.O. no.15, s.2019). Others may use their degree or units in graduate studies as a basis for promotion in the Department of Education.

Table 4. Profile of the respondents in terms of highest in-service training attended (n=135)

Highest in-service training attended	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
District	39	28.89	2
Division	37	27.41	3
Regional	40	29.63	1
National	19	14.07	4
Total	135	100.00	

As evident, the respondents have attended training at the district level, division level, regional level, and national level. It is evident that 39 or 28.89% of the respondents have attended INSET in the district level, rank 2; 37 or 27.41%, division level, rank 3; 40 or 29.63%, regional level, rank 1; and 19 or 14.07% in the national level, rank 4.

This can be deduced that the respondents have been upskilling and reskilling themselves by attending in-service training in the district/division/regional/national level to achieve a better learning outcome (D.O. No. 50, s. 2020). Professional development is also reflected in the KRA 4 of the Individual Performance and Review Form (IPCRF) of teachers in the DepEd. More so, by adhering to the mandates of the Republic Act No. 10912, otherwise known as the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Act of 2016 which needs CPD as the mandatory requirement for the renewal of professional license every three years.

Table 5 reflects the extent of teachers' willingness in the implementation of MDL at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic. Results reveal that the respondents have been very willing in the implementation of MDL with an overall weighted mean of 3.89. Indicator 6 has the highest weighted mean of 4.17 or very willing, rank 1. It can be inferred that the respondents are very willing to distribute the modules to the parents as scheduled every Monday. Indicator 2 has the least weighted mean of 3.16, as willing. This reveals that the teacher-respondents in Tayasan District I are still willing to spend their own resources such as purchasing their own printers, bond papers, and ink for the education of their children.

Table 5. The extent of teacher's willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
1. Writing of modules aligned with the provisions of MELC	3.49	Very Willing	8
2. Reproduction of modules using personal resources (ex. printers, bond papers, ink, etc.)	3.16	Willing	9
3. Orientation of parents in their roles and functions in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL)	4.15	Very Willing	3
4. Communicating learners in their Weekly Home Learning Plan (WHLP)	3.96	Very Willing	5
5. Conduct of simulation in modular distance learning	3.87	Very Willing	7
6. Prompt distribution of modules to parents	4.17	Very Willing	1
7. Prompt retrieval of modules from parents	4.16	Very Willing	2
8. Assessment of learners' outputs according to D.O. No. 31, s.2020 and D.O. No. 8, s.2015	4.10	Very Willing	4
9. Reproduction of supplementary materials for struggling learners	3.92	Very Willing	6
Overall Weighted Mean	3.89	Very Willing	

According to Moore's (1989) theory, there are three main components of transactional distance. The first two are dialog and structure – which relate to teaching procedures and the curricula, thirdly, autonomy – which relates to student's behaviors. The results above can be noted that the teacher respondents are eminently willing to increase dialogue and structure between them and their learners to enhance understanding, whereby transactional distance decreases. Thus, it improves and increases learner's autonomy (Abuhassna & Yahaya, 2018; Nardo, 2017; Öztürk, 2020).

Table 6 displays the factors that deter the implementation of MDL in pandemic time. As evident, the overall weighted mean is 3.18 with a descriptive rating of sometimes. This can be viewed that the respondents have seen that the indicators above in some instances can deter the implementation of MDL.

Table 6. Deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL in pandemic time

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
1. Insufficient funds for module reproduction resulting in more or less 1:4 ratio	3.10	Sometimes	5
2. Parents' resistance to assume mentorship responsibility	3.30	Sometimes	4
3. Parents' low educational background resulting in less desire in coaching their children	3.73	Often	1
4. Inadequate information drive towards school health and safety protocols	2.73	Sometimes	7.5
5. Students' resistance to engaging in study-at-home approach	3.32	Sometimes	3
6. Physical distance from school to home (vice-versa) in the distribution and retrieval of modules	3.55	Often	2
7. Reluctance on the part of parents to interface with teachers due to fear of the existing COVID-19 pandemic	3.00	Sometimes	6
8. Reluctance on the part of teachers to interface with parents due to fear of the existing COVID-19 pandemic	2.73	Sometimes	7.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.18	Sometimes	

Indicator 3 has the highest weighted mean of 3.73 described as often, rank 1. This implies that the respondents have observed that parents' education plays a vital role in facilitating learning for their children. Thus, parent's education level has a positive significant influence on the academic achievements of their children (Rana et al. 2015). Indicator 6, ranks 2 as a deterrent factor in the implementation of MDL with a weighted mean of 3.55, often. This result is valid since most of the schools in the Tayasan District 1 are found in the hinterland.

Indicator 5 with a weighted mean of 3.32, sometimes, rank 3 as a deterrent factor in the implementation of MDL. According to Brookfield (2006), he said there are six reasons why students resist learning such as poor self-image as learners, fear of the unknown, the disjunction between learning and learning styles, apparent irrelevance of the learning activity, inappropriate level of required learning, and students' dislike of teachers.

Significant Relationship between Teachers' Profile and the Extent of Teachers' Willingness in the Implementation of MDL in Pandemic Time

Gender

At 0.05 level of significance and a degree of freedom of 4, the computed chi-square of 1.128 is lesser than the tabulated chi-square of 9.49. This gives the decision rule that the respondents' profile in terms of gender is not significant to its extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD. This further accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of gender and the extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD.

Age

At 0.05 level of significance and a degree of freedom of 20, the computed Chi-square of 15.592 is lesser than the tabulated Chi-square of 31.41. This gives the decision rule that the respondents' profile in terms of age is not significant to its extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD. This further accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of age and the extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD.

Further, the results have shown that there are more respondents in the middle age group compared to retirement age. This implies that the extent of willingness mostly comes from the respondents in the age of 44 and below in which they think more critically than those of retireable age who prefer tranquility and easiness in their decisions (Salthouse, 1992).

Educational Attainment

At 0.05 level of significance and a degree of freedom of 16, the computed chi-square of 14.596 is lesser than the tabulated chi-square of 26.30. This gives the decision rule that the respondents' profile in terms of educational attainment is not significant to its extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD. This further accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of educational attainment and the extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD.

The above results reflect that the extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD in Tayasan District I is not determined by the educational attainment of the respondents. Hence, they are aware of the Basic Education - Learning Continuity Plan of the DepEd where education cannot be hampered and should be delivered to all learners in the Philippines.

Highest In-service Training Attended

At 0.05 level of significance and a degree of freedom of 12, the computed Chi-square of 10.229 is lesser than the tabulated Chi-square of 21.03. This gives the decision rule that the respondents' profile in terms of the highest in-service training attended is not significant to its extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD.

Table 7. Significant relationship between teachers' profile and the extent of teachers' willingness in the implementation of MDL in pandemic time

Profile of the respondents	χ^2 Computed Value	χ^2 Tabular Value	df	Level of Significance	Decision Rule	Remarks
Gender	1.128	9.49	4	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Age	15.592	31.41	20	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Educational Attainment	14.596	26.30	16	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Highest INSET Attended	10.229	21.03	12	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho

Table 8. Significant relationship between teachers' profile and the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL in pandemic time

Profile of the respondents	χ^2 Computed Value	χ^2 Tabular Value	df	Level of Significance	Decision Rule	Remarks
Gender	7.012	9.49	4	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Age	15.535	31.41	20	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Educational Attainment	8.909	26.30	16	0.05	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Highest INSET Attended	22.477	21.03	12	0.05	Significant	Reject Ho

This further accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of the highest in-service training attended and the extent of willingness in the implementation of MDL toward TD.

This reveals that willingness in the implementation of MDL is not associated with the respondents' in-service training attended because DepEd has been providing training or workshops in the conduct of distance learning in different modalities such as Learning Delivery Modality Course for teachers before the implementation.

Significant Relationship between Teachers' Profile and the Deterrent Factors in the Implementation of MDL in Pandemic Time

Gender

At 0.05 level of significance and a degree of freedom of 4, the computed chi-square of 7.012 is lesser than the tabulated chi-square of 9.49. This gives the decision rule that the respondents' profile in terms of sex is not significant to the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL in pandemic time. This further accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of sex and the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL.

This can be conceived that the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL are not influenced by the gender of the respondents because they are aware of the gender and development programs of the DepEd which promotes equal rights of men and women in decision-making.

Age

At 0.05 level of significance and a degree of freedom of 20, the computed chi-square of 15.535 is lesser than the tabulated chi-square of 31.41. This gives the decision rule that the respondents' profile in terms of age is not significant to the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL in pandemic time. This further accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of age and the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL.

This clearly implies that the respondents' age does not contribute to the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL because as an employee in the DepEd, they are directed to exercise their duties and responsibilities regardless of age.

Educational Attainment

At 0.05 level of significance and a degree of freedom of 16, the computed chi-square of 8.909 is lesser than the tabulated chi-square of 26.30. This gives the decision rule that the respondents' profile in terms of educational attainment is not significant to the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL. It can be noted that the determined deterrent factors are learner and parent's related matters.

Highest In-service Training Attended

At 0.05 level of significance and a degree of freedom of 12, the computed chi-square of 22.477 is greater than the tabulated chi-square of 21.03. This gives the decision rule that the respondents' profile in terms of the highest in-service training attended is significant to the deterrent factors in the implementation of MDL in pandemic time.

Similarly, pedagogical knowledge and literacy are concerns for first-time distance learning teachers (Kayaduman & Demirel, 2019). The need to promote innovative practice among educators (Arinto, 2016; Talidong, 2020) and the need to sustain innovative practice among innovators are both challenges, and these demands are further contextualized by the Philippine setting.

Conclusion

Teachers' willingness to participate in the implementation of the modular distance learning, not just by virtue of employment with the Department of Education but for the reason that as mentors it is their professional and moral responsibilities to render services to the students who have relied upon the basic education training appurtenant to their academic preparation and professional experiences.

With the exception of the highest level of in-service training attended by the teachers, the rest of the profile variables have no significant relationship, nor have these factors become deterrent to the extent of willingness to implement the MDL. It goes without further saying, that the teachers' willingness to serve is guided and motivated by their inherent traits of service, love, and commitment to their students regardless of time, distance, and circumstances. It is crystal clear that there was a wide disparity in transactional distance between teacher and learner's dialogue due to the use of modular distance learning, completely wanting of face-to-face instruction, hence; asynchronous. But on the other hand, the transactional distance was lessened due to the strong bilateral partnership between teachers and parents (who represented their children in receiving the learning materials in module forms), in mentoring their children (enrolled in the school year 2020-2021) in the teaching-learning process which took place at home.

Recommendations

In the light of the foregoing findings and conclusions, the following are recommended. Schools must strengthen the Adopt-A-School program to supplement the resources needed in the reproduction of modules so teachers will not spend their personal resources. More so, schools should encourage parents to continue mentoring and scaffolding the learning process of their children through the MDL modality. In like manner, teachers should conduct home visits while observing the health protocols and provide technical assistance to parents who are less capable of assisting their children in the academic process. Hence, schools should establish programs, for instance, the PLEP Innovation to provide appropriate interventions to those parents with low educational backgrounds and to those who are distant from school in getting and returning the modules.

It is further recommended by this study that the Department of Education should further enhance the teachers' capability building in distance learning education to prepare for the incoming School Year 2021-2022. In these challenging times, schools have to initiate an intervention program that will assess the strengths and weaknesses of the MDL modality and determine if there was an increase or decrease in the transaction between teacher and students in School Year 2021-2022 and thereafter.

References

- Abuhassna, H., & Yahaya, N. (2018). Students' utilization of distance learning through an interventional online module based on Moore transactional distance theory. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 14(7), 3043-3052. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/91606>
- Alea, L. A., Fabrea, M. F., Roldan, R. D. A., & Farooqi, A. Z. (2020). Teachers' Covid-19 awareness, distance learning education experiences and perceptions towards institutional readiness and challenges. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(6), 127-144. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.6.8>
- Arinto, P. B. (2016). Issues and challenges in open and distance e-learning: Perspectives from the Philippines. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 17(2), 162-180. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v17i2.1913>
- Bongco, R. T., & Abenes, R. D. (2019). Clash of spheres - The paradox of being a female teacher in the Philippines. *Beijing International Review of Education*, 1(2-3), 443-459. <https://doi.org/10.1163/25902539-00102012>
- Bozkurt, A. (2019). From distance education to open and distance learning: A holistic evaluation of history, definitions, and theories. In S. Sisman-Ugur & G. Kurubacak (Eds.), *Handbook of research on learning in the age of transhumanism* (pp. 252-273). IGI Global.
- Briones, L. M. (2020, June 19). *Adoption of the basic education learning continuity plan for school year 2020-2021 in light of the Covid-19 public health emergency*. Department of Education. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/DO_s2020_012.pdf
- Brookfield, S. D. (2006). *The skillful teacher: On technique, trust, and responsiveness in the classroom* (2nd ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Kayaduman, H., & Demirel, T. (2019). Investigating the concerns of first-time distance education instructors. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 20(5), 85-103. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v20i5.4467>
- Moore, M. G. (1989). Three types of interaction. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 3(2), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08923648909526659>
- Nardo, M. T. B. (2017). Modular instruction enhances learner autonomy. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 5(10), 1024-1034.
- Öztürk, S. Y. (2020). An investigation of student teachers' engagement in autonomous outside-the-classroom learning activities. *PASAA: Journal of Language Teaching and Learning in Thailand*, 59, 131-153.
- Preacher, K. J. (2001, April). *Calculation for the chi-square test: An interactive calculation tool for chi-square tests of goodness of fit and independence* [Computer software]. <http://www.quantpsy.org/chisq/chisq.htm>
- Salthouse, T. A. (1992). Reasoning and spatial abilities. In F. I. M. Craik & T. A. Salthouse (Eds.), *The handbook of aging and cognition* (pp. 167-211). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Talidong, K. J. B. (2020). Implementation of emergency remote teaching (ERT) among Philippine teachers in Xi'an, China. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), 196-201.